

KOL Message: Real World Evidence for Pharmaceutical Research and Development

By Sajan Khosla †

Real World Evidence (RWE) is a broad term that has been adopted within the pharmaceutical industry due to its ability to bring together two complex sub terms; the Real World Data (RWD) and the Evidence subsequently synthesised from those data. Therefore to truly define RWE one must define the RWD. RWD in its most traditional form is data collected in routine clinical practice that contains information pertinent to a patients' health status [1]. The evidence generated is a result of statistical, epidemiological and scientifically robust methodologies that can make use of these data.

With this definition and this understanding of RWE it becomes clearer to explain the variety in the types of skills required within industry to deliver innovative RWE and also why RWE is not just one thing, as the permutations of sources of data together with the types of analysis lead us into hundreds if not thousands of types of RWE designs.

The popularity of RWE within the pharmaceutical industry stems from the value the capability has brought into the industry, starting from traditional pharmacovigilance with safety focused epidemiology. The expansion into Medical Affairs with post marketing commitments with the use of RWE and the use of RWE to fill evidence gaps that emerge from randomised clinical trials. The primary inflection point being in the early 2010's where the notion of scalable data sharing or acquisition became a reality. Industry teams developed statistical infrastructure to house large complicated medical claims datasets and developed a traditional "Stats and Programming" capability around those data. The second inflection point was cloud computing, when it was realised these large complex data that often took two to three days worth of processing to run a single script, could be done in milliseconds, a dynamic shift was observed with how the industry could use these data. With that data strategies and ultimately types of methodologies emerged and evolved as the industry had the ability to balance out that benefit vs. resource risk.

The view so far has been introspective from an industry view but outside industry academic partners, data owners and health systems were also experiencing their own market forces that evolved their depth and expertise. Especially in academia where public health units started to specialise in causal modelling methods [2], capabilities like target trial emulation [3] and the multi purpose use of Propensity Score Weighting/Matching [4] became clear.

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The value cycle of RWE has also shifted with the change in types of data that feed into our evidence packages and the methodologies that are available for the industry to deploy. With that maturity in the use of RWE over the past decade, nuances of how to position RWE in the pre-regulatory domain is more clearly defined to its counterpart in the post-regulatory marketing space, where RWE has traditionally been organised.

A personal hope for RWE is that this evolution in the types of data follows a path by which health systems become more sophisticated in the variety of RWD that is available, to some extent this is happening with use of data linkage and tokenisation [5]. This evolution of the data brings a rise in the methodologies we deploy to robustly assess and evaluate RWE, such as Quantitative Bias Analysis (QBA) [6]. This together with the evolving structure global regulators are developing to allow for RWE packages to be evaluated as part of the approval process gives me confidence that the evolution of the term RWE is not over.

[1] Klonoff DC. The New FDA Real-World Evidence Program to Support Development of Drugs and Biologics. *J Diabetes Sci Technol*. 2020 Mar;14(2):345-349. doi: 10.1177/1932296819832661. Epub 2019 Mar 12. PMID: 30862182; PMCID: PMC7196856.

[2] Crown WH. Real-World Evidence, Causal Inference, and Machine Learning. *Value Health*. 2019 May;22(5):587-592. doi: 10.1016/j.jval.2019.03.001. PMID: 31104739.

[3] Simpson A, Ramagopalan SV. RWE ready for reimbursement? A round up of developments in real-world evidence relating to health technology assessment; part 7. *J Comp Eff Res*. 2022 Jul;11(10):699-701. doi: 10.2217/ce-2022-0071. Epub 2022 May 4. PMID: 35506497.

[4] Franklin JM, Patorno E, Desai RJ, Glynn RJ, Martin D, Quinto K, Pawar A, Bessette LG, Lee H, Garry EM, Gautam N, Schneeweiss S. Emulating Randomized Clinical Trials With Nonrandomized Real-World Evidence Studies: First Results From the RCT DUPLICATE Initiative. *Circulation*. 2021 Mar 9;143(10):1002-1013. doi: 10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.120.051718. Epub 2020 Dec 17. PMID: 33327727; PMCID: PMC7940583.

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[6] Thorlund K, Duffield S, Popat S, Ramagopalan S, Gupta A, Hsu C, Arora P, Subbiah V. Quantitative bias analysis for external control arms using real-world data in clinical trials: a primer for clinical researchers. *J Comp Eff Res*. 2024 Mar;13(3):e230147. doi: 10.57264/ce-2023-0147. Epub 2024 Jan 11. PMID: 38205741.

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